

Let's BEGIn Bacoor City! – Policy analysis of the barangay e-governance innovation network program amidst a global health pandemic

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Abstract

Since March 13, 2020, the Philippines has been on one of the most stringent lockdowns in modern world history, all face-to-face transactions were halted, and everyone shifted to e-commerce and virtual education to avoid widespread community transmission of the COVID-19 virus. The rationale for implementing e-governance is that it would allow different government agencies, both in the national and local branches to deliver more cost-effective public service and foster inter-collaborative work among different government stakeholders. E-governance likewise increases public trust resulting in increased utilization and accessibility of public services cutting on costs, speed and offering improved convenience. Moreover, this is also a move by the national government to foster a digital economy thus, contributing to ease of business. The government program promises to improve public trust and improve delivery of public processes through digitization of services and public data. The program also involves promotion of citizens' awareness and understanding of their community characteristics, promotion of effectiveness and efficiency in service delivery, facilitation, and promotion of transparency and accountability of government in operations and services, promotion of linkages and interaction between government and citizens and other groups in society and most importantly, creates links and bridges between the government, business, non-government organizations (NGOs) and other groups in society to be inclusive and participatory. The city of Bacoor and its citizens would greatly benefit from this program particularly in disaster response, health crisis management, and effective and efficient delivery of social services.

Keywords: *E-governance; Health; Disaster management; Bacoor; Social development.*

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Introduction and Policy Context

The global scenario particularly in the Philippines dramatically shifted from an all-out face-to-face transactional economy to now a virtually dependent economy because of a pandemic known as the nCOV-19 that affected virtually all countries in the world. Since March 13, 2020, the Philippines has been one of the most stringent lockdowns in modern world history, all face-to-face transactions were halted, and everyone shifted to e-commerce and virtual education to avoid widespread community transmission of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) virus (Ocampo & Yamagishi, 2020).

The Philippine government, now faced with the challenge of sustaining its impressive growth and making it more inclusive, has strived to implement the e-government approach since 2016. Since then, several innovations were benchmarked to come up with the E-government

Masterplan or EGMP 2022 (DICT, 2019). This project envisioned the Philippine National and Local Government to be “a digitally empowered and integrated government that provides responsive and transparent online citizen-centered services for a globally competitive Filipino nation” (DICT, 2019).

The rationale for implementing e-governance is that it would allow different government agencies, both in the national and local branches to deliver more cost-effective public service and fosters inter-collaborative work among different government stakeholders. E-governance likewise increases public trust resulting in increased utilization and accessibility of public services cutting on costs, speed and offering improved convenience. Moreover, this is also a move by the national government to foster a digital economy contributing to ease of business.

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) in the improvement and facilitation of government procedures, activities, transactions and processes has proved to be a very effective link towards attaining inclusivity and participation among the citizens (Ona et al., 2012). Siar (2005) studied the Philippine e-government start-up and stressed that “e-governance may be defined as the application of ICTs in refining and strengthening the interaction between government and citizens (G2C) and government, business and other groups (G2B), as well as improving internal government processes (G2G) to streamline and improve public administration”.

Various purposes of e-governance were interpolated in the study of Siar (2005). Attributed functions were first to promote citizens’ awareness and understanding of their community characteristics, second is to promote effectiveness and efficiency in service delivery, third is to facilitate and promote transparency and accountability of government in operations and services. Likewise, information and communication technology (ICT) and e-governance promote linkages and interaction between government and citizens and other groups in society and most importantly, creates links and bridges between the government, business, non-government organizations (NGOs), and other groups in society to be inclusive and participatory.

Table 1. Functions of e-governance in the national and local government (Siar, 2005)

Function	Relevant information / resource
1. Promote citizens’ awareness and understanding of their community characteristics.	Historical, cultural, physical, social, and economic information; Political organization; Community / city news
2. Promote efficiency and effectiveness in the delivery of front line services.	Government services and procedures; Downloadable forms
3. Promote transparency and accountability of government in operations and services.	Government services and procedures; Programs and projects; Procurement information and bid invitations; Ordinances; Financial information
4. Promote citizens’ awareness of the policymaking process and their participation in decision making.	Information on local policymaking process; Ordinances; Online polls and surveys
5. Promote linkage and interaction between government and citizens and other groups in society: both vertical communication (between government and citizens and other groups in society) and horizontal communication (among the different groups in society).	E-mail address, phone number of city officials, feedback form, online polls / surveys (online communication); Discussion forum, chat, and other similar online facilities (horizontal communication)
6. Promote linkage between government and business.	Procurement information and bid invitation; Economic and business profile; Investment opportunities; Tourism information

Innovation in Governance: BEGIn (Barangay E-Governance and Innovations Network) Program

The BEGIn Program or the Barangay E-Governance and Innovations was a brain product of Techstatic IT solutions, an all-Filipino IT Solutions company that focuses on the modernization of local government units (LGUs) through modular approaches to building solutions to problems in local governance. The BEGIn program is a very promising solution to red-tape and the long bureaucratic process involved in face-to-face government transactions.

The BEGIn program promises transformation of information into safe, fraud proof and reliable data for government processes. It is a simple, unified and factual way to deliver an organized data information system towards a ready and well-informed group of citizens. The program features a digitized information database that empowers the barangay at the Micro Level through the use of relevant technology and a user-friendly application. Data may include residential information, social demographics and household data.

In terms of relational database, most particularly data important for Social Development, Health and Education, the BEGIn platform is centralized and offers to provide high speed database searches and comprehensive residential info, which is needed by concerned government agencies, in turn, this saves the government costs, improves efficiency and increases public trust among others.

There are certain identified benefits of the BEGIn program. These include comprehensive disaster management, top class contact tracing, improved first line relief operations and makes the citizens well-informed with the capability to perform locality wide announcements and most importantly improves the efficiency of the Barangay functional roles.

Innovative City in Focus: The City of Bacoor and the BEGIn Program

The adoption of the BEGIn Program to the seventy-three (73) barangays in the first class city in the Province of Cavite is through the initiatives of Bacoor City Mayor Lani Mercado-Revilla. According to Mayor Revilla, it is the “New Normal” way of governance for the Local Government of Bacoor, Cavite amidst this pandemic by implementing the e-governance platform. This will come in the form of a public-private partnership between Bacoor LGU and Techstatic IT Solutions.

The BEGIn program would be initiated for usage of the 73 barangays for monitoring, and surveying of database and socio-demographics of the whole city. The first project to be performed would be the citywide survey regarding the COVID-19 vaccine to be administered to the citizens of the city. Mayor Revilla likewise stressed that the program could also be used on intensified disaster and relief operations, implementation of the National ID system, and the improvement of delivery of social and health services to the Bacoor citizens (Deña, 2021).

Another major predictor for the approval of this program by the City Council is the aspiration to make the City of Bacoor to become a ‘smart city’, being a model of digitalized governance and the hope to maintain the streak of the city in taking the Seal of Good Governance from the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG). The program will start with 500 enumerators to start the citywide survey in COVID-19 vaccination.

The City Government of Bacoor is positive that the BEGIn program will have a positive impact on the delivery of basic services to the citizens and also improve transparency efforts and the programs that facilitate inclusion and participation of the citizens in city building and program implementation (Gut, 2021).

Figure 1. City of Bacoor Mayor Lani Mercado-Revilla during the BEGIn Launching

Policy Implications on Social Development Implementation

E-government in the Philippines is envisioned to create “a digitally empowered and integrated government that provides responsive and transparent online citizen-centered services for a globally competitive Filipino nation.” In the study of Rimjhim & Kumar (2018), digital governance addresses the wide gap between the society and the government by making it more accessible, easier and more doable.

E-governance assures that the tenets of democracy through democratization is achieved and assures that the government and the people are in close contact to one another, and that more trustful and powerful interactions occur. Moreover, transparency is present and is constantly assured by e-governance. All of the details needed are visible to the citizens reinforcing the trust of the people to the government.

One strength of e-governance in social development is the fundamental assurance of effectiveness and efficiency of delivery of social services since all services are electronically delivered. Likewise, record keeping, and document tracking is better than in personal transactions. According to Bataineh and Al-Shanab (2016) and Kolachalam (2012) as cited in Rimjhim and Kumar (2018), the government should develop citizen-centric e-government models, benefiting citizens and businesses most, while cost saving is concomitant, thus, eradicating several other bottlenecks hindering development of a locality or nation. However, there are certain disadvantages and challenges that hinder the full enactment of e-governance among different localities. For example, in the Philippines, there are certain localities with a dearth in internet

connection and connectivity apparatuses. It will be a major step back and a barrier for the implementation of e-governance (Pasco et al., 2017).

Amplifying the existing problem is the presence of a Digital Divide. There is a huge gap between the people and localities who do not have solid infrastructure thus affecting their connection and the use of e-governance. This was further reinforced by Rimjhim and Kumar (2018) who stated that “this digital divide is mainly due to poor penetration of ICT amongst regions like rural and urban, class like educated and uneducated, poor and rich to name a few,” this directly affects the willingness and the drive of the citizens to participate fully. Moreover, in this connected age of technology, there are possibilities wherein individual data may be hacked by miscreants for personal gain, to be able to protect it, there should be a strong framework for protecting this data from being misused illegally. Data collection should be a minimum to ensure that not much data is divulged in case of hacking (Rimjhim & Kumar, 2018).

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is very innovative for the Bacoor Local Government to venture and explore the powers of e-governance particularly during a prolonged period of lockdown attributed to a global pandemic. Adding to the innovation is the LGU participation in Public-Private Partnership to implement E-Governance. The product of this collaboration is the BEGIn Program for the city of Bacoor.

The program promises to improve public trust and improve delivery of public processes through digitization of services and public data. The program also involves promotion of citizens’ awareness and understanding of their community characteristics, promotion of effectiveness and efficiency in service delivery, facilitation and promotion of transparency and accountability of government in operations and services, promotion of linkages and interaction between government and citizens and other groups in society and most importantly, creates links and bridges between the government, business, non-government organizations (NGOs) and other groups in society to be inclusive and participatory.

The city of Bacoor and its citizens would greatly benefit from this program particularly in disaster response, health crisis management, and effective and efficient delivery of social services. However, there are certain points and recommendations that could be performed to further improve the program:

1. The presence of these need-specific digital services would highlight the uniqueness of the program over its private counterparts.
2. Another recommendation is addressing the digital divide through education. Education is still the most effective strategy for building people’s awareness and imparting the correct knowledge and attitude.
3. The use of e-governance and digital platforms to encourage open discussion and participation in policy making, city concerns and ordinances.

Finally, the BEGIn Program is a promising solution to address city services and provide the needs of the Bacooreños during the COVID-19 pandemic and towards the New Normal.

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References

- Bataineh, L., & Abu-Shanab, E. (2016). How perceptions of e-participation levels influence the intention to use e-government websites. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 10(2), 315-334. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TG-12-2015-0058>
- Deña, C. B. (2021, March 4). *Bacoor LGU launches barangay digital registration for COVID-19 vaccine*. Manila Bulletin. <https://mb.com.ph/2021/03/04/bacoor-lgu-launches-barangay-digital-registration-for-covid-19-vaccine/>
- Department of Information and Communications Technology. (2019). *E-Government masterplan 2022*. Department of Information and Communications Technology. <https://dict.gov.ph/ictstatistics/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/EGMP-2022.pdf>
- Gut, L. (2021, March 17). *COVID-19 vaccination starts in Bacoor City*. Sentinel Times. <https://www.sentineltimes.net/2021/03/covid-19-vaccination-starts-in-bacoor.html>
- Kolachalam, S. (2012). An overview of e-government. *Economia Aziendale Online*, (1), 1-12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13132/2038-5498/2004.1.1-12b>
- Ocampo, L., & Yamagishi, K. (2020). Modeling the lockdown relaxation protocols of the Philippine government in response to the COVID-19 pandemic: An intuitionistic fuzzy DEMATEL analysis. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 72, 100911. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2020.100911>
- Ona, S. E., Ulit, E., & Hanna, N. K. (2012). The Philippines: The quest for genuine e-development. In N. K. Hanna & P. T. Knight (Eds.), *National strategies to harness information technology* (pp. 153-194). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-2086-6_5
- Pasco, R. C., & Ona, S. E. (2017, June 20-22). *Enabling e-government in the Philippines: Uncovering gaps and opportunities in policy development* [Paper presentation]. DLSU Research Congress 2017, De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines. <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/dlsu-research-congress-proceedings/2017/HCT/HCT-II-025.pdf>
- Rimjhim, & Kumar, V. (2018). Social implications of e-government. In H. Bansal, G. Shrivastava, G. N. Nguyen, & L. M. Stanciu (Eds.), *Social network analytics for contemporary business organizations* (pp. 35-50). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-5097-6.ch003>
- Siar, S. V. (2005). E-governance at the local government level in the Philippines: An assessment of city government websites. *Philippine Journal of Development*, 32(2), 135-168.